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Credit to Private Individuals and Innovation at a Global Level

It decreased on average by 32.97% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered

Within the global innovation index, a section relating to credit is proposed which constitutes a macro-category. This size of credit is determined by three components, namely: finance for startups, credit to the private sector as a percentage of GDP, and loans from microfinance institutions as a percentage of GDP. The analyzed data available refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://composite-indicators.jrc.ec.europa.eu/explorer/explorer/indexes/giii/global-innovation-index>

Credit to Private Individuals and Innovation at a Global Level in 2022. The supply of credit to the private sector represents a crucial indicator of a country's ability to support innovation and economic development. In 2022, the global ranking of this offering sees Hong Kong SAR, China at the top with a score of 100, reflecting an extremely favorable financial environment for the private sector. Hong Kong, with its robust banking system and efficient regulation, positions itself as a leader in the provision of credit, significantly supporting innovation through easy access to capital. In second place is Cambodia with a score of 76.6, which is surprising for a developing economy. This could indicate a proactive government policy in favoring the private sector, perhaps through reforms that improve accessibility to credit and incentivize foreign investment. The United States follows with 69.8, confirming its prominent position as one of the most advanced and innovative financial markets in the world, where private businesses have broad access to the financing needed to develop new technologies and grow. Countries such as Nepal and Denmark, with scores of 65 and 62.4 respectively, demonstrate that access to credit is a global phenomenon that does not depend exclusively on the level of economic development. Nepal, in particular, highlights how emerging economies can improve access to credit to support private sector growth. Denmark, known for its strong welfare state and mature economy, maintains a balance between regulation and access to finance. New Zealand and Japan, with scores of 61.6 and 59.6 respectively, demonstrate well-developed banking systems and policies conducive to entrepreneurship and innovation. Switzerland (57.9) and Norway (56.7), both with highly developed and stable economies, also offer high access to credit, efficiently supporting the private sector. Among Asian countries, South Korea (54.8) and Malaysia (55.7) stand out for relatively high access to credit, which contributes to a favorable environment for innovation and technological development. Finland (51.6) and the United Kingdom (51.4) continue to support their advanced economies with strong financial infrastructures. Southeast Asia shows a strong presence, with Thailand (55.4) and Singapore (50.3) boasting robust financial systems, promoting private sector growth. Other European countries such as Sweden (50.1), Estonia (47.4), and France (47.3) confirm the trend of high credit supply on the continent. Countries such as

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China (44.7) and Spain (41.1) show significant differences compared to Western standards, but continue to provide access to credit consistently to support economic growth. The United Arab Emirates (40.8) and Luxembourg (40) are also positioned in the medium-high range, benefiting from sophisticated banking systems. In Latin America, Chile (39.5) and Peru (51.5) stand out as regional leaders in the provision of credit to the private sector, demonstrating the importance of sound financial policies for economic development. On the other hand, countries such as Brazil (22.1) and Argentina (17.3) highlight greater challenges in terms of access to credit, reflecting economic and political difficulties. In the Middle East, Israel (38.1) and Kuwait (36.6) demonstrate financial systems capable of supporting innovation, although there is room for improvement compared to world leaders. Saudi Arabia (32.4) and Oman (30.4) indicate more limited access to credit, a sign of the challenges in economic diversification outside the energy sector. In Eastern Europe, Moldova (38.6) and Slovakia (33.6) have moderate access to credit, which may reflect the post-Soviet economic transition. Countries such as Poland (22.2) and Hungary (28) show lower values, suggesting areas for improvement in their financial infrastructure. African economies such as Tanzania (51.5), Namibia (26.5) and South Africa (31.4) vary greatly, with some countries offering surprisingly high access to credit, while others struggle with less developed financial systems. Egypt (17.6) and Kenya (8.3) reflect the difficulties in accessing credit that many African countries face, limiting the growth potential of the private sector. In South Asia, India (26.4) and Bangladesh (31.4) show significant efforts to improve access to credit, although there are still significant barriers to overcome. Pakistan (14.1) has a low score, highlighting structural problems in the financial system. Finally, the extremely low scores of countries such as Iraq (1.2), Zimbabwe (2.1) and Ethiopia (0) indicate serious supply gaps credit, reflecting economic instability and weak financial policies. These countries face significant challenges that hinder private sector development and innovation, underscoring the need for deep reforms to improve access to credit. In summary, access to credit for the private sector varies significantly globally, influenced by economic, political and institutional factors. Countries with developed banking systems and favourable policies tend to offer greater access, supporting innovation and economic growth. However, many emerging and developing economies still face significant challenges in improving credit supply and thus supporting private sector progress.

Private Credit and Innovation at a Global Level between 2013 and 2022. In recent years, the trend in demand for private credit has shown significant variations at a global level, reflecting the economic, social and political changes of each country. Data available from 2013 to 2022 indicates that some countries have experienced an increase in demand for credit, while others have seen a drastic decrease. These changes can be attributed to several reasons, including economic stability, technological innovation and government policies. Hong Kong SAR, China, showed a moderate increase in credit demand, going from an index of 95.4 in 2013 to 100 in 2022, with an absolute change of 4.60 and a percentage of 4.82%. This increase can be attributed to economic resilience and the adoption of innovative technologies in the financial sector. On the other hand, countries such as Cambodia recorded a significant increase in credit demand, with an absolute change of 16.50 and a percentage of 27.45%, going from 60.1 to 76.6. This suggests an improvement in economic conditions and an increase in access to financial services for the population. In the United States, however, the demand for credit decreased significantly, going from 93.4 to 69.8, with an absolute variation of -23.60 and a percentage of -25.27%. This decline can be attributed to various factors, including the 2008 financial crisis, which led to increased caution in taking on debt by both consumers and financial institutions. Countries like Nepal have seen a dramatic increase, with an absolute change of 32.30 and a percentage change of 98.78%, going from 32.7 to 65. This could be indicative of rapid economic

growth and significant expansion of the financial sector. In Europe, Denmark saw a decrease in credit demand, with a drop from 90.7 to 62.4, an absolute change of -28.30 and a percentage change of -31.20%. Similarly, other European countries such as Switzerland and Sweden recorded significant decreases, of -23.20 and -19.60 points, respectively, with percentages of -28.61% and -28.12%. These declines may reflect a combination of austerity policies, economic uncertainties and changes in consumer preferences towards more sustainable borrowing. Japan and South Korea both experienced reduced credit demand, with declines of -22.30 and -12.40 points respectively. These declines may be related to economic stagnation and demographic challenges, such as an aging population, which negatively influence the propensity to consume and borrow. In Latin America, countries such as Brazil and Mexico saw a reduction in credit demand, with changes of -4.10 and -8.00 points respectively. These changes can be attributed to the region's economic and political instabilities, which have led to greater uncertainty and caution in taking on debt. In Africa, countries such as Nigeria and Ghana recorded the steepest declines in credit demand, at -26.30 and -29.40 points respectively. This may be indicative of economic difficulties and structural limitations that prevent wider access to financial services. In contrast, some emerging countries have shown an increase in demand for credit. For example, Tanzania and Thailand recorded increases of 20.10 and 12.40 points respectively, with percentage changes of 64.01% and 28.84%. This may reflect greater economic stability and an expansion of financial markets in these regions. Italy, similarly to many European countries, saw a decrease in credit demand, with a drop from 53.9 to 35.8, an absolute change of -18.10 and a percentage of -33.58%. This decline may be linked to the economic difficulties the country has faced in recent years, including public debt problems and stagnant economic growth. Countries such as China and India saw minimal changes in credit demand, with modest increases of 3.20 points and decreases of 9.10 points respectively. The situation in China may reflect a balance between economic stability and government policies aimed at controlling excessive debt. In India, however, the reduction could be linked to economic reforms and structural challenges in the financial sector. Finally, countries such as Indonesia showed minimal changes in credit demand, with a marginal increase of 0.20 points. This suggests relative stability in the financial sector, with little significant change in the propensity to borrow among the population. In conclusion, the analysis of data on credit demand for private individuals from 2013 to 2022 highlights a number of global trends influenced by various economic, social and political factors. While some countries have seen a significant increase in demand for credit, reflecting economic growth and an expansion of financial services, others have experienced dramatic declines, indicative of economic and political challenges negatively impacting access to and appetite for credit. These variations highlight the importance of local contexts and government policies in shaping consumer financial behavior.

Conclusions. If we consider the supply of credit to private individuals and innovation we can note that between 2013 and 2022 this value decreased on average by 32.97% for the countries considered. Among the countries that have seen significant growth in the supply of credit to private individuals and innovation are Nepal with +98.78%, Madagascar with +71.95%, Tanzania with +64.01 %, Qatar with +48.65%, Turkey with +33.21%. However, there are also countries that have seen a significant reduction in the value of credits towards private individuals and innovation, namely Nigeria with -87.67%, Uganda with -88.59%, Zimbabwe with -90, 23%, Ghana with -93.93%, and Ethiopia with -100%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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